

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No. B440
Date: 27(Z)-28 Apr 2009
Take Off: 23:49:56Z
Landing: 04:53:38Z
Flight Time 5h 03m 42s

Campaign: MEVEX Maritime (Dawn) Flight 2
Operating Area: Ocean, E of Muscat

POB	Position	Name	Institute	Logs y/n
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight	
2	Co-pilot	Luc Lathouwers	Directflight	
3	CCM	Gaynor Ottaway	Directflight	
4	Mission Scientist	Dave Kindred	Met Office	
5	Flight Manager	Steve Devereau	FAAM	
6	Core Chem / AVAPS	Doug Anderson	FAAM	
7	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	FAAM	
8	ARIES	Stuart Rogers	Met Office	
9	SWS / SHIMS	Martin Glew	Met Office	
10	Wet Neph / CVI / IIR	Andy Wilson	Met Office	
11	MARSS	James Bowles	Met Office	
12	Mission Scientist 2	Dave Pollard	Met Office	
13	Mini-LIDAR	Joss Kent	Met Office	
14				
15				
16				
17				
18				
19				

Missing Log Sheet	Reason
Pre-flight log	No log available
Brief	No brief on FAAM website
De-brief	Sortie De-brief yet to be created by ???
Core Chemistry / TDLAS	no In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
PSAP log	No log as PSAP pump/filter info included on Flight Summary page
Wet Neph	No log passed to FAAM yet
CVI	No log passed to FAAM yet
SWS	No log passed to FAAM yet
Mini-LIDAR	No log passed to FAAM yet
IIR	No IIR log is provided for the Flight Folder

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	03 Nov 2009	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

The following avi format video recordings should be available at the BADC in core_processed/faam-video :

No video on BADC @ 31 Dec 2009

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B440
 Date: 28th April 2009 (preflight 27th)
 Project: MEVEX Maritime
 Location: Oman

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
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233636		Start-Up	0.16 kft	266	
234119		taxy	0.16 kft	266	
234208		ASPs	0.16 kft	355	opened
234956		T/O	7.1 kft	082	
235725		JW	11.2 kft	118	zero
235844		CPC	13.3 kft	120	start
241758	242614	Profile 1	21.0 - 13.0 kft	115	
242810	245033	Profile 1	13.1 - 2.1 kft	272	
244857		BBR	2.9 kft	114	retract cover
245241	245356	Profile 1	2.1 - 1.1 kft	350	
245559		Video	1.1 kft	144	start
250028		Video	1.1 kft	279	recording crash
250157	250319	Profile 1	1.1 - 0.50 kft	131	
250436	250830	Run 1.1	0.55 - 0.52 kft	033	
250637		Video	0.52 kft	027	restart
251314	251841	Run 1.2	0.58 - 0.55 kft	209	
252052	252715	Run 1.3	0.56 - 0.52 kft	026	
252123		Heimann cal	0.56 kft	018	
253016	253344	Run 1.4	0.60 - 0.53 kft	212	
253352	253756	Profile 2	0.60 - 3.1 kft	210	
254058		TWC	3.2 kft	069	reset
254146		Heimann	3.1 kft	046	cal
254301	254831	Run 2.1	3.1 kft	023	QNH 1009 (ship)
255225	255829	Run 2.2	3.1 kft	217	
260720	261553	Run 2.3	3.1 kft	030	
260749		Video	3.1 kft	025	crash & restart
261755		Heimann	3.1 kft	297	cal
261935	262734	Run 2.4	3.1 kft	213	
262747	262929	Profile 3	3.2 - 5.1 kft	209	
262829		Video	4.0 kft	209	crash & restart
263220	263925	Run 3.1	5.1 kft	017	
263327		Heimann	5.1 kft	038	cal
263515		JW	5.1 kft	032	zero
264316	264931	Run 3.2	5.1 kft	215	
264944	265352	Profile 4	5.1 - 9.1 kft	207	
265607	265714	Profile 4	9.1 - 10.1 kft	027	
265725	270449	Run 4.1	10.1 kft	029	
270828		Heimann	10.1 kft	234	cal
270911	271453	Run 4.2	10.1 kft	203	
271508	271913	Profile 5	10.1 - 6.1 kft	205	
272051	272201	Profile 5	6.1 - 5.1 kft	040	

272211	273905	Run 5.1	5.1 kft	021
272334		Heimann	5.1 kft	028 cal
274411	274924	Run 5.2	5.1 kft	205
275343	275946	Profile 6	0.52 - 8.0 kft	023
280112	280654	Profile 6	8.0 - 14.0 kft	148
280829	281552	Profile 6	14.0 - 22.0 kft	008
281553		Sonde 01	22.0 - 0.12 kft	008
285338		Land	0.12 kft	086 Muscat
285616		ASP	0.12 kft	086 closed
285616	285926	Pirouette	0.12 kft	086
290721		Shutdown	0.11 kft	266 23 35.36N 58 17.66E

B440 21:44:50–29:10:43

GLNG_PARA0581, GLAT_PARA0580

B440-#mevexViRClog

*** Opened channel log for #mevex at 28/04/2009 04:01:21

[2009/04/28 04:01] *** FAAMOpsDetach (~vircuser@85.154.2.202) has joined #mevex
[2009/04/28 04:01] *** Mode change [+nt] on #mevex by photon.ge.phy.umist.ac.uk
[2009/04/28 04:01] [FAAMOpsDetach] anybody there?
[2009/04/28 04:10] *** Server connection lost
[2009/04/28 04:11] *** Server connection lost
[2009/04/28 04:12] *** FAAMOpsDetach (~vircuser@85.154.2.202) has joined #mevex
[2009/04/28 04:12] *** Mode change [+nt] on #mevex by photon.ge.phy.umist.ac.uk
[2009/04/28 04:16] [FAAMOpsDetach] testing
[2009/04/28 04:18] *** Server connection lost
[2009/04/28 04:22] *** Server connection lost
[2009/04/28 04:22] *** Nickname is already in use: FAAMOpsDetach
[2009/04/28 04:23] *** Server connection lost
[2009/04/28 04:23] *** FAAMOpsDetach (~vircuser@85.154.2.202) has joined #mevex
[2009/04/28 04:23] *** Mode change [+nt] on #mevex by photon.ge.phy.umist.ac.uk
[2009/04/28 04:26] *** FAAM_flt_man (~GLUXE@203.38.13.30) has joined #mevex
[2009/04/28 04:26] <FAAM_flt_man> hilloo
[2009/04/28 04:34] [FAAMOpsDetach] hillo
[2009/04/28 04:36] [FAAMOpsDetach] all go well?
[2009/04/28 04:38] <FAAM_flt_man> yes, pretty good
[2009/04/28 04:46] *** Server connection lost
[2009/04/28 04:46] *** FAAMOpsDetach (~vircuser@85.154.2.202) has joined #mevex
[2009/04/28 04:52] *** Server connection lost
[2009/04/28 04:54] [FAAMOpsDetach] i've renamed the satmap files on the faam website so the pos doesnt show
[2009/04/28 04:54] *** FAAMOpsDetach (~vircuser@85.154.2.202) has joined #mevex
[2009/04/28 05:00] <FAAM_flt_man> clivir
[2009/04/28 05:02] *** FAAM_flt_man (~GLUXE@203.38.13.30) has left #mevex
[2009/04/28 05:04] *** Server connection lost
[2009/04/28 05:06] *** FAAMOpsDetach (~vircuser@85.154.2.202) has joined #mevex
[2009/04/28 05:06] *** Mode change [+nt] on #mevex by photon.ge.phy.umist.ac.uk
[2009/04/28 05:06] [FAAMOpsDetach] Jon has gone to Seeb with car so let me know if anyone needs transport and i
will get him to return via the security gate
[2009/04/28 05:13] *** Server connection lost
[2009/04/28 05:13] *** FAAMOpsDetach (~vircuser@85.154.2.202) has joined #mevex
[2009/04/28 05:13] *** Mode change [+nt] on #mevex by photon.ge.phy.umist.ac.uk
*** Closed channel log for #mevex at 28/04/2009 05:17:21

Cloud Physics Flight Log B440

Date: 27/04/09	Operator: Map	DRS Time: 21:50	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	AUX1 Time: +0	AUX2 Time: +0
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DAU2 Disk space?

	PCASP SPP-200		CDP		PCASP		2DC		FFSSP		SID3	
Operated?												No
Pre-flight checks	Vref		Ref V (~3):	2.84	Vref (>7):	unknown	El#1 V (>1):	-1.3V	Ref V:	3.3	Comms?	N
	Sample flow	1.35			Flow (~1):	0.7	El#32 V (>1):	-1.3V				
	Sheath flow	16.78			Pressure:	1007						
					Temp (NDIT)	31.6						

GMT	Height	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		PCASP		2DC		Habit	FFSSP	SID3	Comments
		#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	Mean R	#/L	Max R				
23:58:00													Heaters on and SWS cooler not operated
24:09:00													Old PCASP Ch1 noise evident
24:17:28	FL210	0		30	0.1	20	0.06				12		Start Profile 1
24:21:47	FL170	0		30	0.1	25	0.06						
24:22:50	FL160	0		30	0.1	25	0.06						
24:23:59	FL150	0		40	0.1	40	0.06						
24:25:04	FL140	0.1	5	80	0.5	130	0.10						
24:26:13	FL130	0.1	5	120	0.5	110	0.10						
24:29:31	FL120	0.1	7	150	1.5	135	0.11				13		
24:30:44	FL110	0.1	7	170	1.5	140	0.10						
24:31:40	FL100	0.1	7	200	1.5	150	0.10						
24:33:51	FL090	0.05	6	200	1.5	150	0.09				14		Major noise on new pcasp
24:36:33	FL080	0.1	6	250	2	330	0.09						Heaters off
24:38:27	FL070	0.15	6	500	2	410	0.09						
24:42:13	FL060	0.2	6	500	1.5	500	0.08				15		
24:44:01	FL050	0.2	6	550	1.5	540	0.08				16		
24:46:13	FL040	0.1	6	500	2	480	0.09						
24:48:24	FL030	0.2	6	550	2	530	0.09				17		
24:50:35	2000'	0.3	10	800	2	850	0.09				18		
24:53:54	1000'	0.4	7	600	2	800	0.09				19		
25:03:11	500'	0.4	7	600	2	620	0.09				24		End of Profile
01:04:25	500'												Start Run 1.1
01:05:00		0.4	7	600	2	650	0.09				26		

GMT	Height	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		PCASP		2DC		Habit	FFSSP	SID3	Comments
		#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	Mean R	#/L	Max R				
01:07:00		0.4	7	600	1.5	610	0.09				29		
01:08:32													End of Run
01:13:15	500'												Start Run 1.2
01:14:00		0.5	7	600	1.5	630	0.09				34		
01:16:00		0.5	7	550	1.5	660	0.09				37		
01:18:40													End of Run
01:20:50													Start Run 1.3
01:21:00		0.5	7	550	1.5	660	0.09				41		
01:23:00		0.4	7	550	2	640	0.09				42		
01:25:00		0.5	7	600	2	630	0.09				44		
01:27:00		0.5	7	600	2	700	0.09				45		
01:27:19													End of Run
01:30:19	500'												Start Run 1.4
01:31:00		0.5	7	600	2	650	0.09				49		
01:33:40													End of Run & Start Profile 2
01:34:32	FL010	0.5	7	500	2	585	0.09				51		
01:36:12	FL020	0.4	7	550	2	670	0.09				52		
01:38:02	3000'	0.3	7	500	2	430	0.09				53		End of Profile
01:43:06	3000'												Start Run 2.1
01:44:00		0.2	7	450	1.5	470	0.09				56		
01:46:00		0.2	7	450	1.5	460	0.09				57		
01:48:00		0.2	7	450	1.5	500	0.09				58		
01:48:31													End of Run
01:52:28	3000'												Start Run 2.2
01:53:00		0.2	7	450	1.5	450	0.09						
01:55:00		0.2	7	450	1.5	460	0.09						
01:57:00		0.2	7	500	1.5	470	0.09						
01:58:34											Fail		End of Run
02:07:19	3000'	0.3	7	500	1.5	440	0.09				1		Start Run 2.3
02:08:00		0.2	7	500	1.5	480	0.09						FFSSP laser volts low
02:10:00		0.2	7	500	1.5	480	0.09						
02:12:00		0.2	7	500	1.5	440	0.09				2		
02:14:00		0.2	7	500	1.5	470	0.09						
02:15:54													End of Run
02:19:41	3000'												Start Run 2.4
02:20:00		0.2	7	500	1.5	450	0.09						

GMT	Height	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		PCASP		2DC		Habit	FFSSP	SID3	Comments
		#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	Mean R	#/L	Max R				
02:22:00		0.3	7	450	1.5	450	0.09				4		
02:24:00		0.3	7	500	1.5	480	0.09						
02:26:00		0.25	10	500	1.5	460	0.09				5		
02:27:31													End of Run
02:27:47	3000'												Start Profile 3
02:28:29	FL040	0.2	7	400	1.5	340	0.08						
02:29:43	FL050	0.1	5	300	1	190	0.08						End of Profile 3
02:32:13	FL050												Start Run 3.1
02:33:00		0.1	5	200	1	170	0.08				6		
02:35:00		0.1	5	250	1	240	0.08						
02:37:00		0.1	5	300	1	280	0.08						
02:39:00		0.1	5	400	1	410	0.08						
02:39:29													End of Run
02:43:17	FL050												Start Run 3.2
02:44:00		0.1	6	400	1	360	0.08				8		
02:46:00		0.1	6	350	1	310	0.08						
02:48:00		0.1	6	250	1	220	0.08						
02:49:34	FL050												End of Run & Start Profile 4
02:50:39	FL060	0.1	6	100	1	160	0.09						
02:51:45	FL070	0.1	5	300	1.5	170	0.09				9		
02:52:50	FL080	0.1	5	150	1.5	90	0.09				10		
02:53:54	FL090	0.1	5	120	1.5	110	0.10						
02:57:19	FL100												End of Profile & Start Run 4.1
02:58:00		0.1	5	150	1	100	0.10						
03:00:00		0.1	5	200	1	135	0.10				11		
03:02:00		0.1	5	220	1	145	0.09						
03:04:00		0.1	5	200	1	150	0.09						
03:04:50													End of Run
03:08:09	FL100												Start Run 4.2
03:09:00		0.1	5	200	1.5	150	0.09						
03:11:00		0.1	4	200	1	140	0.10						
03:13:00		0.1	4	180	1	110	0.10						
03:14:52	FL100												End of Run & Start Profile 55
03:16:13	FL090	0.1	4	170	1	130	0.09				12		
03:17:26	FL080	0.1	4	170	1	140	0.09						
03:18:10	FL070	0.1	4	50	0.5	50	0.09						

GMT	Height	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		PCASP		2DC		Habit	FFSSP	SID3	Comments
		#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	Mean R	#/L	Max R				
03:21:03	FL060			50	0.08	110	0.08				12		
03:22:03	FL050												End of Profile & Start Run 5.1
03:23:00		0.1	4	250	1	300	0.08						
03:25:00		0.1	4	200	1	200	0.08				13		
03:27:00		0.1	6	300	1.5	320	0.08						
03:29:00		0.1	5	300	1.5	300	0.08						
03:31:00		0.1	7	300	1.5	340	0.09				14		
03:33:00		0.1	7	350	1.5	330	0.09						
03:35:00		0.1	7	300	1.5	280	0.09						
03:37:00		0.1	7	320	1.5	230	0.09						
03:39:06													End of Run
03:43:59	FL050												Start Run 5.2
03:44:00		0.1	7	300	1.5	230	0.08				15		
03:46:00		0.1	7	400	1.5	330	0.08						
03:48:00		0.1	7	300	1.5	320	0.08						
03:49:26													End of Run
03:53:39	500'	0.3	7	300	2	440	0.09				18		Start Profile 6
03:54:53	FL020	0.2	7	450	1.5	370	0.09				19		
03:55:36	FL030	0.2	7	375	1.5	400	0.09						
03:56:17	FL040	0.2	7	350	1.5	280	0.09						
03:57:11	FL050	0.1	5	300	1.5	180	0.09						
03:58:03	FL060	0.15	5	400	1	330	0.08				20		
03:58:54	FL070	0.1	5	300	1	270	0.09						
03:59:46	FL080	0.1	4	200	1.5	190	0.09						
04:01:40	FL090	0.1	4	150	1.5	130	0.09						
04:03:10	FL100	0.1	4	200	1.5	100	0.09						
04:03:57	FL110	0.1	5	200	1.5	125	0.09						
04:04:59	FL120	0.1	4	150	1.5	80	0.09						
04:05:55	FL130	0.1	4	150	1.5	50	0.14						
04:06:56	FL140	0.1	4	100	1.5	80	0.10				21		All heaters on
04:09:21	FL150			50	0.5	20	0.07				22		
04:10:15	FL160			50	0.5	15	0.07						
04:11:09	FL170			50	0.1	15	0.07						
04:12:04	FL180			40	0.1	15	0.07						
04:13:07	FL190			40	0.1	15	0.06						
04:13:56	FL200			30	0.1	15	0.06						

GMT	Height	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		PCASP		2DC		Habit	FFSSP	SID3	Comments
		#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	Mean R	#/L	Max R				
04:14:53	FL210			30	0.1	20	0.06						
04:15:45	FL220			25	0.1	20	0.06						End of Profile CH1 noise in old PCASP
04:30:00													New PCASP noisy in CH 1
													2DC noisy (vibration) rearm 2 1

Post flight

Instrument	Diagnostics		Brief report on instrument performance
PCASP (old)	Vref:	Unkown	Ch1 noise when high and cold
	Flow:	0.7	
2DC	EI#1:	-1.3	
	EI#32:	-1.4	
PCASP SPP-200	Ref V:	7.7	
	Flow:	1.28	
CDP	Laser V:	4.2	Laser voltage higher when cooler as previous flights
FFSSP	Ref V:	0.1	Laser voltage low after fail and restart
SID 3	Laser V:	N/a	
Rack Equipment		1.3GB	Please note SEADAS disk space remaining.

Flight:

B440

KEY

 Not Fitted

 Fitted, Not Operated

 Duff Data

 Minor Problem

 OK

Thermometers

Cabin Temperature:
 Heimann:
 Deiced Temp:
 Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

FWVS:
 Buck CR2:
 General Eastern:
 Johnson Williams:
 Nevzorov:
 Total Water Probe:

Cameras

Downward Facing:
 Forward Facing:
 Rearward Facing:
 Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

Cruciform GPS:
 GIN Applanix:
 INU Honeywell:
 Radar Altimeter:
 RVSM IAS:
 RVSM Static Pressure:
 XR5 GPS:

Misc Core

HORACE:
 AMTG:
 AVAPS:
 Cabin Pressure:
 Printer:
 S9 Static Pressure:
 Satcom C:
 Satcom H (VIRC):
 Turb Centre-Static:
 Turb Left Right:
 Turb Up-Down:
 Turb Horizontal Chk:
 Turb Vertical Chk:
 Weather Radar:
DLUs:
 DLU AERACK:
 DLU BBR Lower:
 DLU BBR Upper:
 DLU Core Chem:
 DLU Core Consoles:
 DLU Port Aft:
 DLU Port Fwd:
 DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

Lower:
 BBR (clear) Lower:
 BBR (IR) Lower:
 BBR (red) Lower:
Upper:
 BBR (clear) Upper:
 BBR (IR) Upper:
 BBR (red) Upper:
 ARIES:
 DEIMOS:
 IR Camera:
 JNO2 Lower:
 JNO2 Upper:
 JO1D Lower:
 JO1D Upper:
 MARSS:
 SHIMS Lower:
 SHIMS Upper:
 SWS:
 TAFTS:

Cloud Probes

2DC:
 2DP:
 FFSSP:
 PCASP:
 PCASP SPP-200:
 2DS:
 ADA:
 CAPS:
 CCN:
 CDP (fuselage):
 CDP (Canister):
 CIP 100 (PIP):
 CIP 25 (CIP):
 CPI:
 CVI (Inlet):
 CVI PCASP-X:
 CVI Ly-A Hygro:
 FSSP (UMan):
 SID1:
 SID2:
 SID3:

Aerosol

CPC 3025A:
 CPC 3786 H2O:
 Filters 47mm:
 Filters 90mm:
 Neph - Dry:
 Neph - Wet:
 PSAP:
 AMS:
 CPC (AMS):
 SMPS (AMS):
 CPC 3010A (CVI):
 INC:
 Mini-LIDAR:
 SP2:
 UHSAS:
 VACC:

Chemistry

CO Aerolaser 5002:
 NOx TE42C:
 Ozone TE49C:
 Ozone TE49:
 SO2 TE43C:
 TDLAS (NIR) CH4:
 TDLAS (NIR) CO2:
 FAGE:
 Formaldehyde:
 NOx FAAM:
 NOxy:
 ORAC:
 PAN:
 PERCA:
 Peroxide:
 PTRMS:
 TDLAS (1C):
 WAS Bags:
 WAS Bottles:
Misc Non-Core
 CASI/ATM:
 LIDAR (big):
 LTI:
 SAW Hygrometer:

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B440

Date: 27/28 April 2009

Instruments

cloud physics

SID3 not operated

old pcasp works ok below fl180, noisy above, channel 2 & higher ok

new pcasp noise from SWS 28V ? data not recorded after short start recording

CVI – ok

IIR – good

wet neph returns zero above 3000ft

dry neph ok

Nevezorov; failed sensor, not operated

Chemistry – good data tdlas required restart

AVAPS – gps signal in aircraft ok but sonde parachute failure & no launch detect

MARSS – good data

SWS/SHIMS -lower shims not operated

Sws nir dropped out briefly

ARIES – good data

Mini Lidar – good data

filters – not flown

FWVS – PC crashes at low level

SATCOM-H: mpds service would not connect

GIN – serviceable

Aircraft

Satcom-H Calls

nil

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) ¼ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by:

ARIES flight log

Flight: B440 page 1 of 2

Date: 27/APR/09 Operator(s): S. Rogers Res: 1 Gain A: 2 B: 2

Loc./Notes: MEXEX: Ship wake (28/APR/2009 Local)

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
~21:35	—						Power On - ok (01:30 local - do how we suffer for our science)
23 15	—	cal	CH	0	83	32	CH cal
~23:50	TAKE OFF						
00 05 45	FL210	cal	CH	0	81	41	CH cal macro.
00 08 40	"	Nadir/Zen	NZ	0	81	41	Nadir/Zenith 30s macro. end @ 00:18 ↓
00 55 06		cal	CH	0	81	41	CH cal 307.5
01 02 36		cal	CH	0	81	42	CH cal 273.0
01 04 25		cal	CH	0	81	41	CH cal 34.9
01 05 45	500'	480x1	N	0	81	41	Nadir - start after abeam with ship.
01 08 50		cal	CH	0	81	41	CH cal
01 10 24		cal	CH	0	81	41	CH cal
01 11 52	500'	480x1	Z	0	81	41	Zenith
01 17 01		cal	CH	0	81	42	CH cal
01 19 49		cal	CH	0	81	42	CH cal.
01 21 16	500'	480x1	N	0	81	41	⊖ Nadir (Heiman cal ~ 01:22)
01 25 37		cal	CH	0	81	41	CH cal
01 27 56		cal	CH	0	81	41	CH cal
01 29 44	500'	480x1	Z	0	81	42	Zenith
01 35 17		cal	CH	0	81	42	CH cal
01 39 20	3000'	cal	CH	0	81	42	CH cal
01 42 40		cal	CH	0	81	41	CH cal.
01 44 00	3000'	480x1	N	0	81	41	Nadir
01 48 30		cal	CH	0	81	42	CH cal.
01 51 33		cal	CH	0	81	41	CH cal
01 52 55	3000'	480x1	Z	0	81	41	Zenith
01 58 42		cal	CH	0	81	42	CH cal
02 05 16		cal	CH	0	81	41	CH cal
02 07 48	3000'	480x1	N	0	81	42	Nadir
02 11 52		cal	CH	0	81	42	CH cal.
02 13 16		480x1	N	0	81	42	Nadir
02 15 58		cal	CH	0	81	42	CH cal

ARIES flight log

Flight:

13440

page 2 of 2

Date:

Operator(s):

Res:

Gain A: B:

Loc./Notes:

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
02 19 52	3000'	cal	CH	0	81	42	CH cal
02 21 14		480x1	Z	0	81	41	Zenith
02 25 32		cal	CH	0	81	42	CH cal Window 36c Mirror 34c
02 29 38	5000'	cal	CH	0	81	41	CH cal
02 32 20		cal	CH	0	81	41	CH cal
02 33 46	5000'	480x1	N	0	81	42	Nadir
02 37 50		cal	CH	0	81	42	
02 40 06		480x1	N	0	81	41	Nadir Turning
02 41 55		cal	CH	0	81	41	CH cal
02 43 31	5000'	480x1	Z	0	81	42	Zenith
02 47 37		cal	CH	0	81	41	CH cal
02 49 03		480x1	Z	0	81	41	Zenith
02 57 13	FL100	cal	CH	0	81	41	CH cal
02 58 48		480x1	N	0	81	41	Nadir Window: 35c Mirror 24c
03 03 16		cal	CH	0	81	41	CH cal
03 08 41		cal	CH	0	81	42	CH cal
03 10 02		480x1	Z	0			Zenith
03 14 06		cal	CH	0	81	41	CH cal
03 21 55	5000'	cal	CH	0	81	41	CH cal
03 23 13		480x1	Z ^N	0			Nadir
03 27 27		cal	CH	0	81	42	CH cal
03 29 54		cal	CH	0	81	41	CH cal
03 32 36		cal	CH	0	81	41	CH cal
03 33 55	5000'	480x1	Z	0			Zenith
03 38 03		cal	CH	0	81	41	CH cal
03 40 45		cal	CH	0	81	41	CH cal Window 34c Mirror 41c
03 44 -		cal	CH	0	81	41	CH cal
03 45 22	5000' 4000'	480x1	Z	0	81	41	Zenith
03 49 36	↓	cal	CH	0	81	41	CH cal Rapid descent.
04 14 05	FL2001	Nad Zen	NZ	0	81	41	Nadir Zenith 30 sec macro Sande
	Transit to	ooms					End 04:41

Microwave Radiometers FLIGHT LOG		Date	27/04/09	Flight	B440	log pages
Operator(s)	J.Bowles		Campaign	MEVEX		
Departure	Muscat		Arrival	Muscat		

System start

MARSS

Visual pod inspection						Y
Close 3 SSP circuit breakers						•
Close all MARSS circuit breakers						•
FERA on	at time					22:00
Temperature controller initial temps	Ch16	29°C	Ch	29°C	Ch18	29°C
Temperature controller set points		54°C	17	58°C	-20	40°C
MARSS CPU on	at time					22:02
Initial target temperatures	Hot	301.5	Cold	302.5		
Target heating						Y
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						•
Scanning on (LMD box)	at time					22:06
Scan indication	Monitor			•	Visual	•

Deimos

Close all Deimos circuit breakers						
Turn on Deimos CPU						
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						
Start Deimos Software	at time					
Initial target temperatures	Hot		Cold			
Target heating						
Scan indication	Monitor			•	Visual	•
Weather	Cloud		Precip			
	Surface		Pressure			
	Other					

System functionality check

(after initial system warmup, approx 1 hour)

PC to DRS Time error	$t_{PC} - t_{DRS} +$	0	at time	23:36:10		
Brightness temps 'sensible'						•
Target temps	MARSS:	Hot	344.56	Cold	301.73	
	Deimos:	Hot		Cold		
Channel gains 'sensible'	Ch1 A	Ch3 A	Ch1 B	Ch3 B		
	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)		
	Ch16	Ch17	Ch18	Ch19	Ch20	
	(40-44)	(45-49)	(40-44)	(40-44)	(44-48)	
	44.81	29.21	39.88	44.57	40.25	

Power changeover

Headset on before start						•
Listen to engine start sequence	4, 3, 2, 1.					•
LMD off (3 switches, bottom to top)						•
Exit Deimos Software (x)						
POWER CHANGEOVER						
LMD on (3 switches, top to bottom)	then pushbutton					•
Restart Deimos Software						
System running again	at time					

